

**THE MODERN APPROACHING TO EDUCATION: IN INSTITUTIONS OF
HIGHER TECHNICAL EDUCATION WHICH SPECIALIZED FOR THE
TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE**

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***Abstract.** The main goal is to conduct profile-oriented teaching of foreign languages in technical universities in accordance with the requirements of the modern era through the effective use of methods of a modern approach to education. The content and technology of education must correspond to the goals and objectives of specialist training, taking into account the specifics of future professional activity, which involves the formation of professional experience based on the principles of problem-solving, interdisciplinary interdependence and complementarity.*

Today it is already obvious that learning in an information and educational environment increases the effectiveness of education in general and learning a foreign language in particular. But one of the problems is that the huge generational gap in computer literacy levels has put teachers in a difficult position with students for the first time. Modern computer technologies, inaccessible to teachers and students who have worked for many years in higher education institutions, open up great opportunities for teachers and students in the information space to acquire knowledge and skills.

***In this article,** much attention is paid to the problem of improving the quality of teaching using methods of studying a foreign language in technical universities.*

This corresponds to the social order of society for the training of a competent specialist with the possibility of increasing his education in the field of educational information.

At the same time, modern requirements pose new tasks for education: the education and development of an internationally oriented personality, the humanistic development of foreign language learners in the context of a dialogue of cultures. A modern specialist must have knowledge about the political and economic system, culture, way of life of the country to which the language he is studying belongs, and the worldview of representatives of the nation whose business partner he may become in the future. To increase its effectiveness in the real communication process, it is necessary to purposefully teach the use of this knowledge. In modern conditions, foreign language classes in technical universities must be treated as a complex educational product that has a multifaceted and clear professional focus. The purpose of higher professional education is training in the basics of the humanities, social, economic, mathematical or natural sciences (depending on the direction), a higher profession that gives the graduate the opportunity to successfully work in the chosen field of activity and have universal knowledge. and special knowledge that contributes to his social mobility and stability in the labor market is education.

Within the framework of this concept, the purpose of studying the subject “Foreign Language” is the acquisition of general cultural knowledge, instrumental knowledge and professional knowledge. The acquisition of the knowledge listed above is a means of foreign language intercultural communication in the spheres of everyday and sociocultural communication, a tool for searching and analyzing foreign sources of information, a tool for professional communication that allows you to solve professional problems in all types of speech activity, taking into account the historical, cultural, political and psychological characteristics of foreign partners .

*When we talk about **scientific innovation**, first of all, we mean improving the quality of higher education, which determines the level of development of the state*

and becomes a strategic direction that ensures their social security and scientific and economic potential.

Studying a foreign language at technical universities involves mastering it as a means of intercultural communication in the field of higher and postgraduate education to achieve educational and professional goals, as well as a means of self-education in the field. professional interests.

For students of technical universities, studying a foreign language is a means of obtaining new information from sources of information in another language, communicating with foreigners, exchanging information, improving their cultural level, etc. means, along with other academic subjects, a foreign language performs serious educational functions, that is formation of a developed personality.

According to a number of researchers, learning a foreign language is necessary to ensure the best performance of professional activities and deepening specialization.

Most researchers understand this function as the ability of a language to assimilate new technical information, but the influence of a foreign language on professional training cannot be limited to this. The language should help to better master the chosen specialty, expand the student's worldview and deepen his knowledge through the direct use of foreign technical information. Therefore, a foreign language in higher education is a university course that is closely related to other subjects and should fulfill its role in the training of a specialist.

If teaching methods have traditionally dominated teaching practice, the modern tradition is the more active use of projective methods based on the development of cognitive needs associated with professional motives, so that with the help of a foreign language students expand their professional knowledge and horizons. When students understand that a foreign language is a means of obtaining personal, valuable information from foreign literature, the need to acquire new knowledge in this area leads to speech activity.

The practical use of this information in the implementation of speech activity awakens in students a feeling of satisfaction of cognitive needs and has a positive effect on their attitude towards a foreign language. Consistent preparation for this is carried out from the first days of language classes. In these lessons, students become familiar with terminology that is close to their future specialization. Considering that the study of a foreign language is specialized, teachers of a technical university should focus students' attention on the importance of the analyzed phenomena for their future specialization.

As a result, the issue of using new information technologies in teaching English is becoming increasingly relevant. The use of new information technologies in teaching foreign languages means not only the practical use of modern technical means and technologies, but also the use of new forms and methods of teaching a foreign language, as well as an approach to the learning process as a whole. One of the main tasks of the teacher is to intensify the activity of each student and create conditions for his creative activity. It is quite obvious that the use of computer and multimedia tools not only helps to implement a student-oriented approach to learning, but also ensures individualization and differentiation taking into account the level of knowledge of students.

The use of computer technologies brings learning closer to real life, helps to use students' interest in computer activities to increase their interest in a foreign language. Multimedia technologies are undoubtedly an innovation and make it possible to make positive changes in the traditional process of teaching a foreign language. Multimedia programs make the process of learning a foreign language more effective, since their use stimulates several channels of perception at once and affects different types of memory: visual, auditory, emotional, motor. They direct students' attention to the important points of the material presented and create visual, effective images - pictures, diagrams, diagrams, graphic compositions, which has a positive effect on the quality of learning a foreign language.

When using computer technology, we are faced with a high level of emotionality in the process of learning a foreign language. On the one hand, computer programs affect various types of senses, which increases the visual richness of the material, making it brighter and more convincing. On the other hand, the process of teaching a foreign language begins to be more creative and provides students with freedom of understanding. At a certain stage of training, they can be involved in creating works on the computer - projects in the form of presentations. Such creativity, which corresponds to the most significant interests of students, stimulates enthusiasm for learning a foreign language due to the attractiveness of working with computers.

We would like to emphasize that supervision by a teacher who has appropriate training and can teach students how to carefully select information is extremely important. It is quite natural that a teacher who realizes that young people are becoming more familiar with the new information environment experiences psychological anxiety. In addition, it is very difficult to focus the attention of students born in the information age only on traditional teaching methods.

In the context of changing educational content, ICT offers great opportunities to increase student enthusiasm and develop strong language habits. Computer-based training programs have many advantages over traditional teaching methods. These programs allow you to develop different types of speech activity and combine them in various combinations, help to understand linguistic phenomena, form language skills, create communicative situations, automate language and speech actions, and also ensure the implementation of an individual approach and intensification. independent work of students. The computer allows the student to use all three channels of perception: auditory, visual and kinesthetic, which allows increasing the volume of material studied and the strength of assimilation, significantly improves the status of students in the educational process, and increases cognitive abilities. student activity and maintains interest in the subject, as well as students' independent activity expands its field, creates the opportunity to create situations that are personally

important for each student, and allows the use of the Internet as a means of immersion in virtual space.

When evaluating multimedia programs, high school teachers note that electronic learning tools significantly help an English teacher in developing the complex habit of listening to foreign language speech. The combination of various audio materials and video supplements creates rare opportunities to develop the habit of understanding spoken English. In addition, English-Russian and Russian-English dictionaries are a good basis for expanding your vocabulary. Today's vocabulary and grammar tasks are presented in a youth-friendly way. Over time, the lack of tasks on grammar and vocabulary, their superficiality, arises due to the lack of detailed processing of certain language skills. But the arsenal of a modern English teacher allows him to find an informed decision, making the right choice and skillfully combining the best traditional teaching methods and the capabilities of innovative technologies.

Every student studying English in technical universities can easily analyze any electronic educational program in their future activities and how useful the English subject is for developing listening or speaking skills, expanding vocabulary or processing grammatical events, their traditional ones will be able to compare the effectiveness of methods and decide which one is better in each specific case.

Many questions depend on the teacher and his desire to use information technology in foreign language lessons. Can a computer replace a teacher? - you can safely answer the question: no, it can never be replaced, but a teacher who knows information technology can replace him.

In the methodological material we presented, we set ourselves the goal of talking about the advantages of using information and computer technologies (ICT) in English lessons and the rules for their use in the educational process. To achieve a truly modern quality of education, the task of today's English teacher is not only to master ICT, but also to understand how the approach to the relationship between the functions of the educational process has changed. In modern education, the

traditional leading and controlling function of the teacher is gradually being replaced by a directing and systematizing function. Thus, the purposeful joint activity of a teacher and a student in an information and educational environment (IEE) can be fully realized only in such conditions. If the main task of the teacher in traditional education was to give the student certain knowledge and develop a number of skills, then the goal of training is to help the student set cognitive and creative tasks and solve them, as well as find, use and create information, get acquainted with the information space - this learn.

Keywords: *modern approach to education; new form and methodology of teaching; scientific potential; information Technology; the role of a foreign language in the learning process; speech activity; educational process; computer and multimedia; advantages of using information; modern requirements; professional experience; in the labor market; social mobility and stability.*

Introduction. From the point of view of the relevance of the topic , more attention is paid to the problem of improving the quality of teaching in the methodology of teaching a foreign language in technical universities. This corresponds to the social order of society for the training of a competent specialist with the opportunity to improve his education in the field of educational information. It is the quality of education, and primarily higher education, that determines the level of development of states and becomes a strategic area that ensures their social security and scientific and economic potential.

The material studied makes the issue of using new information technologies in teaching English even more relevant. The use of new information technologies in teaching foreign languages means not only the practical use of modern technical means and technologies, but also the use of new forms and methods of teaching a foreign language, as well as an approach to the learning process as a whole. One of the main tasks of the teacher is to intensify the activity of each student , to create conditions for his creative activity. It is quite obvious that the use of computer and

multimedia tools not only helps to implement a student-centered approach to learning, but also ensures individualization and differentiation taking into account the level of knowledge of students. Many questions depend on the teacher and his desire to use information technology in foreign language lessons. Can a computer replace a teacher ? - you can safely answer the question: no, it can never be replaced, but a teacher who knows information technology can replace him.

In the article we presented, we set ourselves the goal of talking about the advantages of using information and computer technologies in English lessons and the rules for their use in the educational process. To achieve a truly modern quality of education, the task of today's English teacher is not only to master information and computer technologies, but also to understand how the approach to the relationship between the functions of the educational process has changed. In modern education, the traditional leading and controlling function of the teacher is gradually being replaced by a directing and systematizing function. So information only under such conditions, the purposeful joint activity of a teacher and a student can be perfectly implemented in an educational environment. “If the main task of a teacher in traditional education was to give the student certain knowledge and develop a number of skills, then the goal of learning in an educational environment is to help the student set cognitive and creative tasks and solve them , and for this to find, use and create information, communicate him to the information space means to teach him how to be” [3, p.37].

The content and technology of education must correspond to the goals and objectives of specialist training, taking into account the specifics of future professional activity, which involves the formation of professional experience based on the principles of problem-solving, interdisciplinary interdependence and complementarity.

In terms of theoretical knowledge, modern requirements pose new tasks for education: the education and development of an internationally oriented personality, the humanistic development of foreign language learners in the context of a dialogue

of cultures. A modern specialist must have knowledge about the political and economic system, culture, way of life of the country to which the language he is studying belongs, and the worldview of representatives of the nation whose business partner he may become in the future. To increase its effectiveness in the real communication process, it is necessary to purposefully teach the use of this knowledge. In modern conditions, foreign language classes in technical universities must be treated as a complex educational product that has a multifaceted and clear professional focus. "The purpose of higher professional education is training in the basics of the humanities, social, economic, mathematical or natural sciences (depending on the direction), higher education, which gives the graduate the opportunity to successfully work in the chosen field of activity, to have universal and specialized knowledge that contributes to his social mobility and stability in the labor market is obtaining vocational education" [2, p.43].

Within the framework of this concept, the purpose of studying the subject "Foreign Language" is the acquisition of general cultural knowledge, instrumental knowledge and professional knowledge. The acquisition of the knowledge listed above is a means of foreign language intercultural communication in the spheres of everyday and sociocultural communication, a tool for searching and analyzing foreign sources of information, a tool for professional communication that allows you to solve professional problems in all types of speech activity, taking into account the historical, cultural, political and psychological characteristics of foreign partners.

Thus, profile-oriented teaching of a foreign language at a technical university for a modern specialist:

- using reading skills for the purpose of reading, reviewing, searching, familiarizing and studying texts suitable for one's specialty, as well as obtaining and processing information in accordance with the intended purpose from electronic sources of information;

- learn the habits of listening to news on a topic relevant to your specialty, divide information according to communicative purpose;

- express your opinion in oral and written texts, demonstrating knowledge of grammar and special terminology;
- conduct a reasoned dialogue: ask clarifying and polemical questions, add/clarify this or that point of view, support/refute the interlocutor's arguments and at the same time demonstrate that communication has speech etiquette in a wide variety of situations;
- make information/messages on a given topic: present the topic, dividing it into structures, select the problem being discussed, consider its various aspects, present and justify your position;
- speak on the topic: briefly and logically justify your position, briefly summarize the discussion;
- depending on the planned speech product (brief information, commentary, summary), it involves the formation of foreign language knowledge, which makes it possible to grasp a summary of oral and written text.

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From the point of view of practical significance, the acquired theoretical knowledge of the language should help to better master the chosen specialty, expand the student's worldview and deepen his knowledge through the direct use of foreign technical information. In this sense, the computer, being one of the technical information tools, plays a key role in the educational process. The computer has fundamentally entered our lives. Modern students take it for granted, as a simple household item. For today's student, a computer means progress, success and the spirit of the times. This fact cannot be denied when organizing the educational process. "The use of computer technologies brings learning closer to real life, helps to use students' interest in computer activities to increase their interest in a foreign language. Multimedia technologies are undoubtedly an innovation and make it possible to make positive changes in the traditional process of teaching a foreign language" [5, p.52]. Multimedia programs make the process of learning a foreign language more effective, since their use stimulates several channels of perception at once and affects different types of memory: visual, auditory, emotional, motor. They direct students' attention to the important points of the material presented and create visual, effective images - pictures, diagrams, diagrams, graphic compositions, which has a positive effect on the quality of learning a foreign language.

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“Today it is already obvious that training in information - educational environment increases the effectiveness of education in general and foreign language learning in particular. But one of the problems is that the huge gap between generations in computer literacy levels has put teachers in a difficult position with students for the first time. Modern computer technologies, inaccessible to teachers and students who have worked for many years in higher educational institutions, open up great opportunities for teachers and students entering the information space to acquire knowledge and skills” [6, p.73]. We would like to emphasize that supervision by a teacher who has appropriate training and can teach students how to carefully select information is extremely important. It is quite natural that a teacher who realizes that young people are becoming more familiar with the new information environment experiences psychological anxiety. In addition, it is very difficult to focus the attention of students born in the information age only on traditional teaching methods.

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If teaching methods have traditionally dominated teaching practice, the modern tradition is the more active use of projective methods based on the development of cognitive needs associated with professional motives, so that with the help of a foreign language students expand their professional knowledge and horizons. . When students understand that a foreign language is a means of obtaining personal, valuable information from foreign literature, the need to acquire new knowledge in this area leads to speech activity.

As a result, the practical use of information acquired during speech activity awakens in students a feeling of satisfaction of cognitive needs and has a positive effect on their attitude towards a foreign language. Consistent preparation for this is

carried out from the first days of language classes. In these lessons, students become familiar with terminology that is close to their future specialization. Considering that the study of a foreign language is specialized, teachers of a technical university should focus students' attention on the importance of the analyzed phenomena for their future specialization.

The formation of basic knowledge of students is one of the most important issues facing higher education institutions in connection with the modernization of the country's education. In this regard, the question of a modern approach to education becomes relevant. The modern approach places certain demands on students and their level of knowledge of a foreign language. Thus, students' knowledge is divided into basic and advanced knowledge. At a basic level, knowledge of language as a means of communication is assumed (a certain vocabulary, knowledge of basic grammatical structures, knowledge of the patterns of language, familiarity with the cultural environment, etc.).

The advanced level involves students solving practical problems in a foreign language, for example, searching for information relevant to their specialty and mastering the materials they will use. This level is interdisciplinary in nature and is assessed not only by the correct use of certain grammatical structures and active vocabulary, but also by the result obtained.

How successful the modern approach to learning is can be assessed by the ability of students in the future to withstand competition in the free labor market with knowledge of a foreign language and take their rightful place not only in their society, but also in the international arena.

Thanks to the acquisition of knowledge in the process of learning a foreign language, students form certain habits that they can acquire in the future during professional activities in the field of economics, commerce and business, and learn various methods for solving cognitive problems and making effective decisions. and achieve goals while overcoming obstacles.

Thus, the modern approach to teaching a foreign language is developing as an alternative to traditional teaching, where knowledge, skills and abilities are acquired, which limits the practical application of students in future professional activities and does not take into account the essence of human competence in conditions of free market competition.

As for practical mastery of a foreign language, students must know the lexical and grammatical program defined by the program, be able to work with business correspondence in a foreign language and prepare various documents in foreign languages.

As you can see, the modern approach: to the educational process, directly to the free and creative thinking of students; the formation of knowledge and skills that prepare a higher school graduate for the social conditions of society; is aimed at independent search for information and the formation of leadership qualities.

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